

تطبيق نظرية التخمين على خطابات مختارة لجورج بوش: مقتطفات خطابات
مختارة في حربه ضد العراق كدراسة حالة

*Applying Appraisal Theory to the Translation of Selected
Speeches of George W. Bush: Selected Excerpts of Speeches in
his war against Iraq as a case study*

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المستخلص:

ان ترجمة الخطابات السياسية الى اللغة العربية يمكن ان تشكل تحدياً بسبب اختلاف الأنظمة التي تحكم كل من المجتمعات التي تحكم المجتمعات العربية والإنكليزية أيديولوجيا و ثقافيا و موقفيا. وان هذا الاختلاف يتطلب وجود عدة إجراءات او معايير لقبول حكم مثل هذه المجتمعات. لذلك ما قد يكون في بعض الأحيان مفهوما و مقبولا بالنسبة للجمهور الذي يتحدث الإنكليزية مرفوضا تماما لدى المتحدثين في اللغة العربية. ان الهدف من هذه الورقة البحثية هو لتسليط الضوء على ترجمة الخطابات السياسية وبالتحديد خطابات الرئيس الأمريكي السابق جورج بوش في حربه ضد العراق عام 2003. سوف نستعرض في هذا البحث مقتطفات مختارة من خطاباته وبعدها نقوم بتحليلها بناءا على نظرية التخمين لمارتن و لويس (2003: 19). و سوف نقوم باقتراح ترجمة ملائمة الى اللغة العربية عند الحاجة. إضافة الى ذلك. ستحاول هذه الورقة البحثية تقديم حلول مناسبة للمشاكل التي قد تواجه المترجم في ترجمة الخطابات السياسية.

ومن المؤمل ان تقدم هذه الورقة البحثية إضافة مناسبة في مجال الترجمة لغرض مساعدة المترجمين بشكل عام و طلبة الترجمة بشكل خاص من اجل تشخيص أي فروقات محتملة في المجالات الايدولوجية و الثقافية والادراكية التي قد تنشأ بين النص الأصلي والنص المترجم ومن شأنها ان تشوه الرسالة التواصلية مما يؤدي الى الخطأ في ترجمتها. إضافة الى ذلك، ستقدم هذه الورقة البحثية بعض الاستراتيجيات لغرض تعويض الفرق الحاصل لمثل هذه المشكلات المحتملة التي قد تعترض الترجمة بشكل عام وترجمة الخطابات السياسية بشكل خاص.

الكلمات المفتاحية: الخطاب السياسي، نظرية التخمين، الايدولوجية، الاعلام، الثقافة

Abstract:

The Translation of political speeches into Arabic can be considered as challenging task due to the difference of ideological, cultural, and attitudinal systems that govern English and Arabic speaking communities. This difference necessitates having many procedures or standards of acceptability to govern each society. Hence, what might be acceptable and pragmatically understandable and interpretable to English readers might be wholly rejected by Arab ones. The aim of this paper is to focus on the translation of political speeches particularly the speeches of the former president of the United States George W. Bush in his war against Iraq back in 2003. We will review selected excerpts of his speeches; then, an analysis will be introduced via applying "Appraisal Theory" Martin and Rose (2003: 19). A suggested translation will be given from English into Arabic when needed. In addition, the paper will suggest a strategy for possible solutions of the problems that may face translators of political speeches.

This paper is hoped to represent a modest contribution in the field of translation in order to help the translators in general and students of translation in particular to recognize any possible areas of ideological, cultural and cognitive gaps that may be raised between S.L. and T.L. communities which may distort the

communicated message and render it unacceptable. Moreover, the paper will suggest some workable strategies as we will see below to bridge these gaps and to overcome such possible problems that may intervene in translation in general and translating political speeches in particular.

Keyword: *political speeches, appraisal theory, ideology, media, culture.*

1. Introduction:

Politicians usually tend to modify reality through their speeches by making them more fluid and probabilistic rather than fixed and determinate (Halliday, 1990: 159). This paper deals with how the political speeches, particularly the speeches of presidents of countries, are made in a way to serve the ideology that the speaker wants to deliver to his audience. If we want to examine these speeches in a different language and in this regard the case here is Arabic, it can be said that they represent two different cultures particularly a source culture (English) and a target culture (Arabic). As a result, the ultimate goal of this paper is to examine if there is a possible option to either concentrate on rendering the “semantic content”, i.e. the message of the speech as it is, or its effect of such a kind of speech, i.e. the function. This variety in the two languages and their cultures represent a challenge for any translator/ interpreter that wants to undertake such a task, what Nord suggests a “documentary and instrumental translations, respectively” (Nord 2007: 47). In addition, the paper will shed light on the linguistic and pragmatic features of English political speeches in general and will discuss a certain theory of translation, that is the theory of “foreignization and domestication” in translation proposed by Venuti (1995). And to see which one is the most suitable strategy to apply that can suit the translation of political genre and its counterpart in Arabic.

This paper is restricted to the written English political speeches of Jorge W. Bush. The paper will try to be highly selective in choosing these speeches to be investigated in order to cover as many aspects under investigation as possible. Finally,

the use of the term translator in this paper includes both the translator in written texts and the interpreter in verbal communication.

2. The role of the translator in political speeches

The critical problem that might be raised in the political speeches is the pure transference from English into Arabic which is supposed to be done on the part of the translator. In such cases the translator is not free from committing mistakes whether these mistakes are on purpose or not. In this sense the translator is going to be considered as a mediator who's task is to transfer the information as it is from the S.L. language into the T.L. language. But it is worth mentioning in this regard that the situation is not that ideal during this process of transference. This will lead the translator to intervene the process of transferring meaning because he can be considered as the controller of the process of communication between the speaker and the foreign audience. In this sense, Pöchhacker (2008: 12-13) proposes the term "contractual medication" in the relationship of the communicative event is distributed among the audience. Hatim and Mason (1997: 122) claim that the role of translators can be considered as "interventionist" because the renderings of such translators will be affected by many factors that precede the translation. These factors can be exemplified by their knowledge and beliefs that they were raised by during their span of life. Van Dijk (2006) proposes a different view for the role of the translator of political speeches. He (ibid) proposes the concept of "manipulator" to the translator but in different stages, that is the first one is "manipulator" when the speaker of the speech who wants to manipulate his audience via his use of lexical choices that are supposed to be directed to his listeners. The translator during the process of understanding these linguistic choices produced by the speaker is going to be manipulated as if he is part of the targeted audience of the speaker. After that, when the translator is going to translate the political speeches form the S.L. to T.L. he is going to be in this case the "manipulator" of the text. It is worth mentioning in this

regard that these hidden ideologies which are supposed to be transferred into the T.L. language might not be fully transferred by the translator as mentioned earlier. Typically, those kinds of translators are normally working with certain media corporations in which these corporations may impose certain regulations on the work of translators as well as in the process of rendering political speeches. These regulation or “set of doxa” can be considered in this sense as ideologies imposed by the media corporation in which the translator has to follow or he might be sacked for. These regulations fall under the category of “institution policy” in which ultimately they will have an impact on the role of the translator in rendering such texts.

3. The hidden Ideology of Political Speeches

Political discourse can generally be described as an act of “legitimation” and face saving of in group acts and “deligitimation and discrimination” of other group acts (Chang and Mehan, 2006: 2). It is governed by the ideology of positive self-presentation and negative other presentation (van Dijk, 2000a: 267). The aim of any political speech and in this paper the speeches of presidents is to drive their audience to a specific point that the speaker wants to deliver to their hearers. Reisigl (2008: 240) gives a definition for political speeches as “structured verbal chain of coherent speech acts uttered on a special social occasion for a specific purpose by a single person and addressed to a more or less specific audience”. In this way, it is clear that the political speeches can be considered as a kind of intentional form and their ultimate goal is to drive the listener to a certain point to get what we can say here a hidden consent to the speaker to do what he is hoping to do. Ideally, the political speeches of presidents are supposed to be prepared by a professional writers or the speaker himself, the president in this case, is well acquainted with the language. In addition, this particular written speech is supposed to be delivered to certain group of people and in this case they are the people of his country or a specific group inside his country if he desire to address them for a specific issue. In this sense, there might be no problem at all on the part of listeners in

understanding the speaker since they both share the same language and culture. The problem might be raised when we are confronted with a foreign president who is delivering a speech about a certain issue that concerns us as a an audience that we are not familiar with the language of the speaker. In this case, if we are not familiar with English in this regard we are definitely going to be in a desperate need for a “mediator” who will in this example is going to transfer the message to us due to his knowledge of that language that the speaker knows (Hatim and Mason, 1997: 37). The mediator in this sense is going to be the translator who can be considered in this case the vehicle to deliver the thoughts of the original speaker to us as the targeted audience. The translator in this case will have the option to translate literary what the original said or not.

3.1. The translation of Ideology in Political Speeches

As mentioned earlier, political speeches make use of the features of different linguistic devices along with their textual features to argue and discuss audience in an effective way. For this reason, Charteris-Black (2005: 181) suggests that the strategy of George W. Bush, the former president of the United States of America, used in his speeches was to describe United States the (US) as synonymous with the advance world in comparison with Iraq at that time in 2002 and to even sometimes of other Arab countries that are accused terrorism and outlaw regimes in his point of view. This description of how the US vocabulary connects with the counterpart Iraqi one in terms of the features “[+emotive] and [-emotive]”. These mentioned features can have various touches on the audience of each of these two cultures of English and Arabic. In addition, this has reflections on the importance of “ethics and language” if the president wants to persuade his citizens of the approval of starting a war (Haskett 2010, Lena 2009).

This way of manipulation by the speaker makes the translation from a source language to a target one a manipulated task because these selected lexemes, and their alignment, their structure in a way that they appear as chosen in a random way and there would be some major thought or idea according to

which these texts are written. These political stretches may look more challenging for translation. At first look, these texts may seem ordinary like other text genres but the implicit ideas that lie behind this word choice; structure and message of these texts are complicated and accurate. Attitudes, ideologies, , and feelings are delivered via language (written or spoken) and through analyzing these speeches, we can for sure able to find out the speaker's ideas and emotions toward an event or phenomenon. The investigation into politicians 'remarks and comments becomes more essential when we find out that their "ideologies and intentions" are not always stated in an explicit and clear way. The text (written or spoken) is like "an iceberg of information," and it is only the "tip" which is actually expressed in phrases and sentences (Van Dijk, 1993: 29). Therefore, he comes with a conclusion that analysis of the overt is very helpful in the study of the underlying ideologies.

3.2. Identity of the political speech

We are going to tackle below some strategies which determine the identity of the political speech because in this way the translator will be able to detect the aim of the political speech which will give him the chance to translate it in an appropriate way. They are as follows:

3.2.1. The Propaganda Nature of Political speech

Politicians try to make use of ambiguous events, situations and objects in the world to serve their own purposes. September events, for example, are tangible acts but, describing them as acts of "defense, aggression, or retaliation" gives them particular meanings (Chang and Mehan, 2006: 1).

However, it is extremely important for propagandists to "make particular sets of meaning and representations dominating over others" (ibid:2). They can, through this way, develop negative "stereotypes" against certain groups and heat prejudice against them (van Dijk, 2000a: 302). Another strategy of propaganda is assigning ordinary events extraordinary meanings. This can be

illustrated through the following excerpt from Bush's speech on Sept. 18, 2001:

“Our compassion and generous citizens have led the first phase in the war on terrorism... citizens near ground zero in New York have provided sandwiches, drinks, and clean clothes to the tired hungry rescue workers.” (cited in Chang and Mehan, 2006: 8).

In this example Bush is trying to makes a comparison through providing food and drink to the aid workers to warlike-events though it is in fact a very ordinary act (ibid: 9).

3.2.2. Evasion and Doublespeak

Evasion is a mitigated form or a different version of refusing to answer questions. Politicians avoid using precise language as in answering any question by “yes” or “no”, and politicians very often resort to circumlocution and deception as a strategy for steering the situation to the destination they want.

Doublespeak, however, as defined by Naoum (2003: 73) is “the language which employs verbal attraction, not to communicate, but to conceal facts [and]... makes the deviated facts easily digested and assimilated by the general public, regardless of the moral responsibility that language should maintain.” Doublespeak is designed “to make lies sound truthful and murder respectable, and to give an appearance of solidarity to pure wind” (Orwell, 1976 cited in Naoum, 2003: 74). Expressions such as “surgical strike” or “smart bombs” (van Dijk, 1995b: 26) which can be found in military propaganda do not serve to communicate in as much as they serve to conceal facts.

3.2.3. Implicitness and Ambiguity

As mentioned earlier, there is a high tendency in political discourse in general and political speech in particular to use implicit rather than explicit meaning. This way of delivering

means to leave many things implicit and make political speeches ambiguous. Ambiguity in this sense can be considered as a powerful tool in which it is employed in an intentional way by political leaders to gain a sort of “immunity”. It works as a shade to hide their real intentions behind, and to leave the listeners in a vast room of maneuvering and for them to get rid from any possible responsibility, since they are not concerned for whatever interpretations people attach to their statements.

3.2.4. Adapting Political Speech

Adaptation comes from the notion of the translator as “an active receptor of the text” (McGuire, 1980: 79). The translator is invited to “approve and disapprove; to express belief, opinion, doubt, to include in the social group or exclude from it, to ask and answer, to express personal feelings, to achieve intimacy” (Halliday, 1973: 316).

Adaptation in a translation strategy is employed when the context referred to in the S.T. does not exist in the culture of the T.T. Vinay and Darbelent (cited in Bastin, 2001: 6). It is used to achieve equivalence in the situational context in cases of cultural mismatches. To Newmark adaptation should be “based on the translator's judgment about his new readers knowledge” (ibid: 6). In other words, the translator adapts the text to the new context to meet the different sociolinguistic, cultural and cognitive needs for the new target readership. For Lefevere (1992a cited in Munday, 2003: 130), however, the most important consideration of adaptation is the ideological one. He states that: “if linguistic considerations enter into conflict with considerations of an ideology... the latter tends to win out.” (Ibid: 131).

4. Methodology

The main purpose of this paper is to determine the possible strategies of translating English political speeches into Arabic by applying Appraisal Theory and Venuti's (1995) framework of “foreignization and domestication “and to seek the solutions of

problems encountered from translating two languages and thus two cultures namely a source culture, English, and a target culture, Arabic. The paper assuming Venuti's model of "foreignization and domestication" (1995) and to review the selected speeches via the analysis of "Appraisal Theory" suggested by Marin and Rose (2013) to fit the aim of this paper. The output of the cooperation between the two models can be considered as a happy marriage with the pragmatic and semantic modules of the political speeches. This will lead to understand the crucial role not only in global planning or understanding of discourse but also in managing a large amount of information to make discourses coherent (van Dijk, 1991: 113; and 2000a: 237).

In order to apply this model on the analysis of English political speeches and a possible suggested translation into Arabic, the following procedure is adopted:

- 1. A selected excerpts of the former American President George W. Bush and his comments regarding Iraq collected from the White House website at www.whitehouse.org. and some comments and analysis will be done on some lexical choices by the speaker.*
- 2. The STs and their suggested renderings are analyzed according Appraisal Theory suggested by Marin and Rose (2013) to and possible suggested translation by adopting Venuti's Model (1992) of "foreignization and domestication".*
- 3. Examining the appropriateness and inappropriateness of these lexical choices in the political speeches and to try to figure out the reason behind choosing these specific lexical choices.*
- 4. The qualitative part includes the analysis of S.T. of the speech based on the analysis suggested by Marin and Rose (2013) "appraisal theory".*

5. Appraisal Theory

The concept of Appraisal comes from the “interpersonal function” suggested by Halliday and Hassan (1975). The core idea of this theory started in a small project on called “Write it Right” at the university of Sydney. Later, Martin and Rose (2003) developed this theory in a more advanced way in order to cope with the issue of why people choose certain lexical choices than others. It is worth mentioning that many scholars like them worked in this theory like Mundy (2003). Martin and Rose (2003: 13) state that appraisal deals with “the interpersonal in language, with the subjective presence of writers/ speakers in texts as they adopt stances towards both the material they present and those with whom they communicate. It is worth noting that the main framework of this theory is in line with the production of speech from the beginning till its end via submitting three main concepts that is “attitude, engagement, and graduation” (Martin and Rose, 2003: 13). These concepts are further subdivided into categories and each category may resemble a certain feature for the linguistic choice which was a figure taken from (Martin

Framework of Appraisal

(Martin and Rose 2003)

We will use the tool of “effect” which falls under the concept of “attitude” since it is workable with political speeches particularly with “emotional reactions”. In addition, the tool of “effect” can be further sub classified into four more variables as “un/ happiness, dis/ satisfaction, in/security, and dis/inclination” (Ibid). These variables can be considered as a measuring tools to check whether George W. Bush in his political speeches against Iraq was applying such “emotional reactions” or not. After giving a brief account of this theory, it now suitable to move on to the practical side of the study as follows.

6. Data Analysis:

As we have mentioned at the beginning of this paper, we will review some selected excerpts of the speeches of the former president of US George W. Bush in his campaign of war against Iraq in 2003. These written texts were delivered verbally in different venues and occasions as well. The aim of these speeches was to gain the support of his nation in his war against Iraq. These speeches can be considered as a challenge to the Arabic translator due to the specific lexical choices of the speaker and the different ideologies between the source culture and the target culture.

Excerpt No. 1

“... a murderous tyrant, who has already used chemical weapons to kill thousands of people. This same tyrant has tried to dominate the Middle East, has invaded and brutally occupied a small neighbor, has struck other nations without warning, and holds unrelenting hostility towards the United States” (Bush, Speech to America, July 9th, 2002).

It is clear from the underlined words that the speaker here is trying to work on the tool of “effect” by using certain lexical choices as “murderous tyrant, used chemical, kill thousands, tyrant, brutally, and hostility”. All these choices can fall under the category of unhappiness and it is obviously clear that the speaker here is trying to “legitimize” and foreground his action of war to his audience. The translator in such cases has to be aware in rendering such speeches due to the sensitive situation of describing such people who are still in power and may even lead to legal consequences to him. Some media corporations with which normally the translators work try to evade such descriptions and may use mild versions of renderings. All in all, it is recommended here that the translator to use “domestication” and transfer these lexical choices as “المجرم الطاغية، استخدام الأسلحة، الكيماوية، قتل الآلاف، الوحشي، العدائي”.

Excerpt No. 2

“We will confront weapons of mass destruction, so that a new century is spared new horrors.” 20 January 2001: Inaugural Address

One of the distinguished lexical choices of George W. Bush in his political speeches is the use of “weapons of mass destruction (WMD)”. This strategy is clear that the speaker wants to work on an important issue that not only the Americans are worry about but the whole world. This repeated linguistic choice “effect” the people’s mind and drive them to agree with what the speaker might say. Another linguistic choice of this excerpt is the use of “new century”. A professional translator in this regard is obliged to render it into “أسلحة الدمار الشامل”. And in the second case of the underlined term, the translator can translate it by making it more domesticated by saying “عصراً جديداً”.

Excerpt No. 3

“We spent a lot of time talking about our mutual interests in Iraq and the Persian Gulf, and from our perspective, as you know, I made the famous statement that our sanctions are like Swiss cheese. That means they’re not very effective. And we’re going to work together to figure out a way to make them more effective” 23 February 2001: Press Conference with Tony Blair.

In this excerpt, George W. Bush is seeking an international support in his war against Iraq. The most interesting point of this speech is the using of “Swiss Cheese”. The translator here is obliged to use domestication by translating it into “عقوبات تشوبها الكثير من الأخطاء” since the Oxford Dictionary defines Swiss Cheese as: “Used figuratively to refer to something that is full of holes, gaps, or defects”.

Excerpt No. 4:

“Those new threats are terrorism, based upon the capacity of some countries to develop weapons of mass destruction, and

therefore, hold the United States and our friends hostage".12
June 2001: Press Conference with Spanish President Aznar.

The speaker, former president of the united states, is trying to grab the attention of the people and in particular his nation by using certain lexical choices as the underlining words showing. The tool of "effect" in appraisal theory can work and the translator has to take into consideration these issues during the process of translation.

Excerpt No. 5:

*"This war will not be like the war against Iraq a decade ago, with a decisive liberation of territory and a swift conclusion". 20
September 2001: Speech to Congress.*

It clear here that the type of the audience here is different and the speaker here took a different strategy in order to convince them to "legitimize" his action by using certain smart words that can show that the will war will be different this time by giving a comparison with a the previous war. In addition, he gives more focus on liberation by collocating a smart word that of "decisive". Finally, he gives a term of "swift conclusion" to give the impression that this war will not cost lives. As a translator, he should pay a careful attention to such choices by the speaker and to translate them as much careful as possible by using "foreignization" strategy. For example we can suggest "نهاية" "خاطفة" to the S.L "Swift conclusion".

Excerpt No. 6

*"The safety of the American people depends on ending this direct and growing threat. Acting against the danger will also contribute greatly to the long-term safety and stability of our world. The current Iraqi regime has shown the power of tyranny to spread discord and violence in the Middle East". 26 February 2002:
Speech on the Future of Iraq, AEI*

As it is obvious from this excerpt, the former president is working of tool of effect in appraisal by using certain lexical choices as shown above. In this example of his speech, he also used the two terms method, as in “direct and ground” and “safety and stability”, to give importance and legitimization for his speech in gaining support for his purpose. The translator need to be full aware of such “traps” in his renderings into Arabic. The reason behind this careful observation is to deliver the intended meaning of the message. The translator may give a rendering like:

تعتمد سلامة الشعب الأمريكي على انهاء التهديد النامي والمتواصل. وان التحرك ضد هذا الخطر سيساهم بشكل كبير على المدى الطويل في سلامة و استقرار عالمنا. لقد اظهر النظام الحالي سلطته الدكتاتورية في نشر الخلاف و العنف في الشرق الأوسط.

Excerpt No. 7

“In all these efforts, however, America's purpose is more than to follow a process -- it is to achieve a result: the end of terrible threats to the civilized world. All free nations have a stake in preventing sudden and catastrophic attacks. And we're asking them to join us, and many are doing so. Yet the course of this nation does not depend on the decisions of others. Whatever action is required, whenever action is necessary, I will defend the freedom and security of the American people”. 28 January 2002: State of the Union Address.

Excerpt No. 8

“We've tried diplomacy. We're trying it one more time. I believe the free world, if we make up our mind to, can disarm this man peacefully”. 21 October 2002: Press Conference, Washington, DC.

Excerpt No. 9

“Over the years, Iraq has provided safe haven to terrorists such as Abu Nidal, whose terror organization carried out more than 90 terrorist attacks in 20 countries that killed or injured nearly 900

people, including 12 Americans". 7 October 2002: Cincinnati, Ohio

Excerpt No. 10

"This man is a man who said he was going to get rid of weapons of mass destruction. And for 11 long years, he has not fulfilled his promise. And we're going to talk about what to do about it. We owe it to future generations to deal with this problem, and that's what these discussions are all about". 7 September 2002: Press Conference with Prime Minister Blair

The speaker is using a different methodology

7. Conclusion

The preceding topics have been primarily concerned with clarifying the issue of translating political speeches into Arabic and some relevant practical examples that showed these cases which tend to happen in such genres. We can conclude that it is very important for any translator of such texts to be full aware of the ideological connections related to the S.L text before starting the process of translation. In addition, the effect of the media institutions that translators normally work for may impose certain regulations that these translators need to follow or they will lose their jobs. These restrictions to their jobs can restrain the translator to transfer the same intended meaning of the text the speaker of the S.L text wanted to deliver. These regulations can be consider in this regard as ideologies which are imposed this time from the T.L text. In addition, censorship can play a vital role in translating these kind of texts. It has been found this this study that applying "appraisal theory" in analyzing this kind of genre and to interpret the real intent of the original speaker can help the translator a lot in his finding for the ultimate equivalence in the target text. Finally, it is recommended to adopt Venuti's Model (1995) in translating such political texts since it can reach the suitable equivalence in translation.

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